

Juxtaposing cases of delegating versus withholding authority of mathematical ideation in early algebra classrooms

Ingrid Ristroph, University of Texas at Austin, ✉ ingrid.ristroph@utexas.edu

Karima Morton, University of North Texas

We will illustrate two cases of teachers implementing the same early algebra lesson exhibiting diametric forms of a teacher practice previously identified in the research literature as a means toward achieving equity—the delegation of mathematical authority. The teacher with greater student achievement gains on an early algebra assessment had greater occurrences of teacher moves that positioned students as having the power to rely on an intellectual authority situated internally or within the community of peers’ “taken-as-shared” knowledge. On the contrary, the teacher with lower gains exhibited greater occurrences of teacher moves that, in effect, resulted in withholding authority from students to form mathematical justifications. Illustrative excerpts of both cases are shared.

Introduction

Non-dominate student populations are subjected to subtle detriments such as having teachers who assume deficits in students, have lower expectations, and hold biases that reinforce stereotypes about who belongs and excels at mathematics (Delpritt, 1992; Flores, 2007; Oakes, 1990; Varelas, Martin, & Kane, 2013). Little is known about how day-to-day teacher instruction either conveys and reinforce or counteracts these messages. One way to counteract these messages is to position students as competent and capable of developing their own mathematical authority (Gresalfi & Cobb, 1996).

Research questions

We explore the ways in which elementary teachers of mathematics confer mathematical authority by asking the following:

How is the power to form and justify mathematical ideas either maintained by the teacher or delegated to students? How does the teacher’s talk moves, uptake of student’s ideas, participation structures, and general academic expectations of students constitute this delegation of mathematical authority? And, finally, how is the degree of delegation of mathematical authority associated with student academic outcome on an early algebra assessment?

Please cite as: Ristroph, I., & Morton, K. (2021). Juxtaposing cases of delegating versus withholding authority of mathematical ideation in early algebra classrooms. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 257–259). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5393147>

Methods

To study these questions, we use a comparative case study to offer a description of interactions in two third grade classrooms teaching an early algebra lesson in an urban, Title 1 school. Videos of two classroom observations are in the process of analysis using open coding in two passes. The first pass we coded for classroom wide instances in which the power to form mathematical decisions is largely positioned within the teacher's power or students'. The second pass is ongoing and is an analysis of teacher's uptake of student's ideas, talk moves, and participation structures.

In order to measure each teacher's students' academic achievement, the gain or difference between a pre- and post-assessment scores of early algebra were used.

Preliminary findings

In order to illustrate the diametrically opposed implementation of delegation of mathematical authority, we will present two episodes extracted from two teachers teaching the same lesson within the same school. Teacher A had a student gain that was almost twice of that of Teacher B. Both excerpts are from the two classrooms as students consider the response to a warm up prompt: "If $a < b$ and $b < c$, how would you describe the relationship between a and c ?"

Teacher A, episode of delegated mathematical authority

Teacher A reviews the problem after having students work on it within small groups.

Teacher: Who has something they want to present and defend? Sebastian, what were you and Jayden saying?

Student 1: If a is less than b and c is bigger than b , then it's bigger than all of them.

Student 2: What's bigger than all of them?

Teacher: Yes, which letter is the largest?

Student 1: The c -- the c is bigger than both the b and a .

Student 3: I don't get it.

Student 1: Look (*standing up, walking to the white board at the front of class*), we can draw a picture to show it.

Figure 1: Student generated representation of the relationship between variables.

Juxtaposing cases of delegating versus withholding authority of mathematical ideation...

The two students presenting then draw a number line exhibiting the relationship $a < b < c$ for the class (see Figure 1). At the end of their presentation, the two students turn to their classmates and ask if others agree.

Teacher B, episode of withheld mathematical authority

Teacher B introduces the problem by having students read the problem out loud. There was no time given for students to consider the task within partners or small groups.

Teacher: Okay, so I'm going to write down two things... (*writes $a < c$ and $a > c$*). (*Turns to class*) Raise your hand if you agree with the first (*gesturing to $a < c$*). Okay, I count 5 votes. (*Writes 4 check marks*). And what about this one... a is more than c ? (*gesturing to $a > c$*)? I see some maybes... one vote?

Student: I just guessed!

Teacher: Yeah? Well, it has to be the first one - a is less than c , because it is less than b and you know b is less than c .

The teacher moves on to the main activity of the lesson without further discussion.

Discussion and conclusion

The practices of Teacher A exhibit delegated mathematical authority in several ways. Firstly, students were given time to consider the task at hand suggesting that the teacher believes it is possible for the students to be successful with the problem and hold such authority. Secondly, the teacher asks students to present and defend their claims and justifications, thus situating mathematical ownership within her students. Lastly, it is evident that a classroom norm that students check for understanding and agreement with their peers. This evidences an established practice of the teacher delegating authority to the students as a whole.

The verbal and non-verbal actions of Teacher B largely withhold the authority of mathematical ideation from the students in that classroom. While the teacher does solicit votes from the students, there is a lack of opportunities for students to make sense of the relationship both in terms of time and peer-to-peer collaboration.

While these two interactions are brief, we maintain they are powerful in contributing to the ongoing conversations about equitable teaching practices in mathematics.

References

- Delpit, L. D. (1992). Education in a multicultural society: Our future's greatest challenge. *Journal of Negro Education*, 61(3), 237–249.
- Flores, A. (2007). Examining disparities in mathematics education: Achievement gap or opportunity gap? *High School Journal*, 91(1), 29–42. <https://doi.org/10.1353/hsj.2007.0022>
- Gresalfi, M., & Cobb, P. (2006). Cultivating students' discipline-specific dispositions as a critical goal for pedagogy and equity. *Pedagogies: An International Journal*, 1(1), 49–57.
- Oakes, J. (1990). Opportunities, achievement, and choice: Women and minority students in science and mathematics. *Review of Research in Education*, 16, 153–222.
- Varelas, M., Martin, D. B., & Kane, J. M. (2013). Content learning and identity construction: A framework to strengthen African American students' mathematics and science learning in urban elementary schools. *Human Development*, 55, 319–339.